

Equilibrium Study of the Complex Formation of some Lanthanide(III) Ions with Schiff Bases derived from some 2-Aminothiazoles and Salicylaldehyde

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Manuscript received 21 May 1987, revised 29 January 1988,
accepted 19 February 1988

THE present communication deals with the determination of stability constants for the interaction of lanthanide(III) ions (La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Tb, Dy and Ho) with the Schiff bases derived from 2-aminothiazole or 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole and salicylaldehyde.

Experimental

Synthesis of ligands: 2-Salicylaldiminothiazole (SB₁) and 2-salicylaldimino-4-phenylthiazole (SB₂) were synthesised¹ by the interaction of salicylaldehyde with the respective aminothiazoles.

A 20% (v/v) methanol-water mixture was used as solvent for equilibrium studies. Rare earth perchlorates were prepared by dissolving the corresponding oxides (A.R.) in perchloric acid. pH measurements were carried out at 20° (±0.1°) with a ECIL 823 expanded scale pH meter (accuracy ±0.05) using glass electrodes in nitrogen atmosphere. CO₂-free sodium hydroxide was used as titrant. The stability constants were determined following the Bjerrum-Calvin titration technique^{2,3} as adapted by Irving and Rossotti⁴. The calculations were done on a DEC-2050 computer by least-square method. The results are depicted in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND CONSTANTS

Protonation constant	Metal(III) ion	Formation constant		
		log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₃
SB ₁ pK _a ^H = 3.95 pK ₁ ^H = 12.00	La	6.92	6.52	6.13
	Pr	7.13	6.92	6.85
	Nd	7.23	7.03	6.90
	Sm	7.53	7.42	7.17
	Eu	7.70	7.42	7.23
	Gd	7.57	7.32	7.20
	Tb	8.02	7.48	7.29
	Dy	8.37	7.69	7.46
SB ₂ pK _a ^H = 3.92 pK ₁ ^H = 11.74	La	7.18	6.61	6.00
	Pr	7.28	6.84	6.29
	Nd	7.44	6.92	6.32
	Sm	7.64	6.97	6.52
	Eu	7.88	7.10	6.70
	Gd	7.73	7.02	6.60
	Tb	7.99	7.20	6.77
	Dy	8.77	7.92	7.58
Ho	8.88	8.10	7.80	

Results and Discussion

The identical nature of the formation curves determined from the ligand-metal ratios of 5:1 and 25:1 ruled out the possibility of formation of polynuclear species. The highest value of $\bar{n} \approx 3$ indicated the combining ratio of metal-ligand as 1:3. The rare earth metal ions binds predominantly to oxygen and weakly to nitrogen. Parallel to the reported trend^{5,6}, a regular increase of stability constants was observed from lanthanum to holmium with the exception of gadolinium due to the combined effect of ligand field stabilisation and the hydration number of the metal ions. The chelate formation also contributes to the greater stability of the present complexes.

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Synthesis and Antibacterial Activity of 4,8-Dimethyl-3-substituted-aminomethyl-coumarins

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Anantapur-515 003Manuscript received 9 December 1987, revised 7 March 1988,
accepted 21 March 1988

COUMARIN and coumarin compounds are reported to possess various physiological activities¹. In our earlier studies² we found an increase in the bacteriological properties of the coumarins by introducing various substituted-alkyl/aryl-aminomethyl linkages at various positions of coumarin nucleus. In the present investigation, we report the synthesis and the antibacterial activity of 4,8-dimethyl-3-substituted-aminomethylcoumarins.

4,8-Dimethylcoumarin³ and 4,8-dimethyl-3-chloromethylcoumarin⁴ are prepared by the reported method. 4,8-Dimethyl-3-substituted-aminomethylcoumarins (3) are prepared by condensing 4,8-dimethyl-3-chloromethylcoumarin with various substituted-amines in dry benzene. The compounds were characterised from their elemental as well as

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